

Vol. I
Number-1

ISSN No. 2319-9687
Jan. -Dec.2012

EDUCATION AND SOCIETY

A PEER REVIEWED JOURNAL

**AN INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
EDUCATION & HUMANITIES**

APH PUBLISHING CORPORATION

ISSN : 2319-9687

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AN INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF EDUCATION & HUMANITIES

Vol. I, Number - 1 January - December, 2012

Chief Editor

Dr. S. Sabu

Co-Editor

S.B. Nangia

APH Publishing Corporation

4435-36/7, Ansari Road, Darya Ganj

New Delhi-110002

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A Comparative Study of Adjustment Level of Male and Female Teachers Working in Government High Schools of Haryana

Dr. Ritu Bala*

ABSTRACT

Higher level of adjustment of the teacher is directly linked with her/his efficiency in her/his work and a vital necessity for the welfare of the students and the nation in general. This research has focused on comparison of adjustment level of male and female teachers working in Government High Schools of Haryana. Mangal Teacher Adjustment Inventory (M.T.A.I.) comprising of 70 items, designed for the preliminary assessment of the adjustment or maladjustment of the teachers of both sexes belonging to Indian schools was used to find the level of adjustment of teachers. It was found that both male and female teachers working in government schools have the same financial and social status, obey same rules and regulations, jobs of are secure and permanent. Therefore, they adjust on equal basis and there is no significant difference in the adjustment level of male and female teachers working in urban area, rural areas and in totality.

INTRODUCTION

The qualitative aspect of education depends entirely on the character and personality of the teacher. A good teacher can communicate the divine spark of learning in a boon where as shallow one will achieve little even with the latest scientific aids. It is a fact that one good teacher can achieve more than a hundred bad or indifferent ones. The efficiency of a teacher is judged through her/his work and behaviour, which is very much dependent on the adjustment with her/him self and her/his environment.

Adjustment is a continuous process that tends to bring out more or less changing attitudes throughout the individual's life. Some adjustment connotes happiness and freedom from personal problems. While for others, it means an unhappy conformity to group demands and expectations. Adjustment is a lifelong process and can be defined as a person's interaction with her/his environment. It is a process in which an individual learns certain ways of behaviour through which she/he enters a relationship of harmony or equilibrium with her/his environment. She/he thereby tries to lead a life acceptable to society (Mohan and Singh, 1989).

Crow and Crow (1956) wrote "An individual's adjustment is adequate, wholesome or healthful to the extent that he has established harmonious relationship between himself and the conditions, situations and persons who comprise his physical and social environment." Gates and his other writers have defined adjustment in the following words "The term 'Adjustment' has two meanings. In one sense, it is a continual process by which a person varies his behaviour to produce a more harmonious relationship between himself and his environment. In other sense adjustment is a state, i.e., the condition of harmony arrived at by a person whom we call 'well-adjusted'."

Professor Rais Ahmed, Chairman of the National Commission on Teacher II, while submitting the report to Government of India said, "We believe teachers are as much instruments of educational change as education could be of social change." A satisfactory adjustment is essential in the job of a teacher. The teacher must know how to be free from maladjustment like aggression, pressures and their personal problems. The advancement in the field of education is possible and depends upon the degree of adjustment and satisfaction of those people who are in the field of education and promote the cause of education. Higher level of adjustment of a teacher causes high-level efficacy in her/his

work or profession. Behavioural adjustment problems in schools are becoming matters of increasing concern among professionals of education and psychology side by side. Well-adjusted teachers are playing very significant role in connection with classroom discipline, growth of the organization and culture of the school itself.

Gupta (1977) while making a study of successful teachers found that success in teaching was significantly related to the areas of home, health, social, emotional and total adjustment, and to professional attitudes, but had no relationship with academic environment. Goyal (1980) in his doctoral research on "Relationship among Attitude, Job Satisfaction, Adjustment and Professional Interests of Teacher Educators in India" found that men and women differ significantly at .05 level in their social adjustment. **Chattopadhyay and Bhattacharya (2002)** found that subjects who were satisfied with their job reported higher job effectiveness and better social and emotional adjustment compared to those who were dissatisfied. Priyadarshani, Nibedita (2004) in her study found that the primary school teachers in the tribal area have been found to have average level of job satisfaction, moderate to high-level of occupational stress and are highly committed to their profession. She also found significant three-factor interaction of sex, marital status, and professional commitment on teacher's job satisfaction. Yadav, R. C. (2011) conducted a study on adjustment of secondary school teachers and observed no significant difference between male, female and rural, urban secondary school teachers. M.G.K.V.P., Varanasi. Goyat (2012) carried out a study to know the gender, demographical and educational impact on teachers adjustment behaviour and observed that there is no significant difference between male, female and rural, urban primary school teachers.

The review of studies shows that a well-adjusted teacher is a source of inspiration to her/his students and a boon to the society. On the other hand, a maladjusted teacher can create havoc with her/his students and her/his own mental health. Thus, the adjustment or the maladjustment of a teacher casts the more deepening effect on the community and the nation than that of any other profession. The fate of the pupils as well as the success or failure of an educational programme hangs on the degree of adjustment of the teacher her/himself. Higher level of adjustment of the teacher is directly linked with her/his efficiency in her/his work and a vital necessity for the welfare of the students and the nation in general.

Therefore, if we wish to bring about improvement in education, we have to identify poorly adjusted teachers, because only a friendly, enthusiastic, secure and well-adjusted teacher can contribute much to the well-being of her/his pupils. On the other hand, the irritable, depressed, hostile, tired and neurotic teacher can create tensions which are disturbing to pupils and which may permanently alter their outlook on life. A maladjusted teacher cannot be allowed to spread the virus of her/his disease to the students or to the society. He must be identified and appropriate steps should be taken to go into the causes of her/his maladjustment.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To make a comparison of adjustment level of male and female teachers working in Govt. High Schools in urban area.
2. To make a comparison of adjustment level of male and female teachers working in Govt. High Schools in rural area.
3. To make a comparison of adjustment level of total male and female teachers working in Govt. High Schools.

HYPOTHESIS

1. There is no significant difference in the adjustment level of male and female teachers working in Govt. High Schools in urban area.
2. There is no significant difference in the adjustment level of male and female teachers working in Govt. High Schools in rural area.

3. There is no significant difference in the adjustment level of all male and female teachers working in Govt. High Schools.

METHODOLOGY

Considering the nature of the problem under investigation descriptive survey method of research was used.

SAMPLING

The population of the study was high school teachers working in Government High Schools of Haryana. The sample consists of 1000 teachers. Out of which there was equal ratio of male and female teachers and equal ratio of teachers working in rural and urban area. The sample was selected by using random sampling of equal allocation.

TOOL

Mangal Teacher Adjustment Inventory (M.T.A.I.) comprising of 70 items, designed for the preliminary assessment of the adjustment or maladjustment of the teachers of both sexes belonging to Indian schools made by S.K. Mangal was used to find the level of adjustment of teachers.

DATA COLLECTION

The researcher personally visited the schools and collected data from the teachers. The teachers were given M.T.A.T. and they were asked to fill up the same.

ANALYSIS AND STATISTICAL TREATMENT OF DATA

Suitable descriptive and inferential statistical techniques: central tendencies, standard deviation and t-test were used to analyze the data. The results of analysis of data are shown in the following tables (1-3):

Table 1: Male and Female Teachers Working in Government High Schools of Urban Areas

Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	SE _p	t-value	S/J.N.S.
Female	250	56.48	5.70	2.39	1.64	N.S
Male	250	57.26	4.89			

Table Value = 1.96

Table-2: Male and Female Teachers Working in Government High Schools in Rural Areas

Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	SE _p	t-value	S/J.N.S.
Female	250	57.33	5.05	2.25	1.14	N.S.
Male	250	56.80	5.26			

Table Value = 1.96

Table 3: Total Male and Female Teachers Working in Government High Schools

Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	SE _p	t-Value	S/J.N.S.
Female	500	56.90	5.40	2.32	0.38	N.S
Male	500	57.03	5.08			

Table Value = 1.96

FINDINGS AND INTERPRETATION

1. The results clearly indicates that female teachers in urban areas had adjustment level with an average of 56.48 and SD 5.70 and male teachers in urban areas had adjustment level with an average of 57.26 and SD 4.89. Male and female teachers in urban areas most probably work at the same place with same type of facilities. The pay-scale of Government schools for either sex is equal. Therefore, they have no problems of adjustment and hence teachers of both the sexes are equally adjusted.
2. The results clearly indicates that female teachers in rural areas had adjustment level with an average of 57.33 and SD 5.05 and male teachers in rural areas had adjustment level with an average of 56.80 and SD 5.26. In rural areas, male and female teachers work in the same environment, draws equal salary and have to obey same rules and regulations. Therefore, they adjust on equal basis.
3. The results clearly indicates that female teachers had adjustment level with an average of 56.90 and SD 5.40 and male teachers had adjustment level with an average of 57.03 and SD 5.08. Both male and female teachers working in Government schools have the same financial and social status, jobs of are secure and permanent and they have no fear of loosing the job. Therefore, the adjustment level of all male and female teachers working in Government high schools is the same.

CONCLUSIONS

On the basis of comparison of mean differences it was found that :

1. There is no significant difference in the adjustment level of male and female teachers working in Government High Schools in Urban Areas of Haryana.
2. There is no significant difference in the adjustment level of male and female teachers working in Government High Schools in Rural Areas of Haryana.
3. There is no significant difference in the adjustment level of all male and female teachers working in Government High Schools of Haryana.

SUGGESTIONS

In the light of the findings of the present study, following are some suggestions that can be used by teachers to improve the adjustment level of the teachers :

1. High school teachers should not be transferred in between the academic session.
2. High school teachers who perform their duties efficiently and sincerely should be given some incentives.
3. High school teachers should not be overburdened by assigning those duties in surveys like surveys of population, surveys for elections, election duties etc.
4. Regular time based promotions should be adopted.
5. The education of the children of high school teachers should be made free in government institutions.

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